

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

D5.1 - Federated Data Analytics for European Biobanks

Work Package:	WP5 - Healthcare Interoperability and Clinical Applications
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Contractual Delivery Date:	31st December, 2021 + 6 month
Actual Delivery Date:	30th June 2022
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Dissemination Level:	Public
Type of Deliverable:	Demonstrator
Grant agreement:	No. 825775 Horizon 2020 (H2020-SC1-BHC-2018-2020)

Type of action:	RIA
Start Date:	1 Jan 2019
Duration:	54 months

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1. Executive Summary

In this report we describe the work done to develop the demonstration tool foreseen in CINECA Task T5.1, i.e. an integration of WP1-3 CINECA services to advance federated biobank search. Starting from the use cases defined during the preliminary stages of the project, the search process was first modeled through UML diagrams and then through mockups representing the future functionalities. The final user interface is pictured in the demonstration section which describes how CINECA services have been combined in an integrated use case to search biobanks and beyond biobanks, how the services will be integrated to serve all WP5 clinical use cases. Regarding the technical part, we describe the architecture of the system, as well as the strategies we have adopted either to access the data when they were exposed, or to store them locally when necessary. Further, we report in this document about the evaluation of the robustness and the search effectiveness of the implemented services.

Furthermore, in order to meet users' expectations regarding the types of findable data, an effort has been made to integrate information related to biobanks, in particular pre-analytical features. Pre-analytical data are describing how tissue and liquid samples are collected and processed. These data are important in determining the quality of biospecimens, i.e. variables of special interest for biobanks include time to storage, storage temperature, tubes and the like. Pre-analytical metadata describing tissue and liquid samples play a critical role in the quality of the biospecimens. We therefore prepared a synthetic dataset of pre-analytical data and developed a set of search services to find, access and ultimately visualize such data.

2. Introduction and objectives

WP5 aims to explore how clinical applications can specifically leverage the secured data federation infrastructure developed within CINECA across WPs 1-4. WP5 requirements have been developed and communicated to other WPs to ensure that WP5 use-cases can be met. Similarly, a list of query examples has been shared with WP1 (e.g. "In this dataset, how many patients with this disease present that particular variant"), while all metadata representation needs have been reported to WP3 [1]. The WP5 team has also been working on making the data accessible.

This deliverable contributes to the following WP5 - Task 5.1 objectives:

- a) to leverage the services delivered by the other CINECA WP, and in particular the query expansion services (WP1 - D1.2), to support clinical research use cases;
- b) to develop a EGA dataset exploration service and demonstrator dedicated to biobanks.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

WP5 aims at exploring clinical dataset management use cases with the following applications: search of biobank data, pathogeny estimation of genomic variants, clinical actionability of variants to support prescription. As the first deliverable of WP5, we establish the service infrastructure layer to tentatively serve most, if not all, WP5 subtasks.

3.2 A set of baseline services

This deliverable describes two specific aims: 1) to develop a generic dataset search-access-exploration pipeline to be used by all WP5 subtasks; 2) to customize the services to specifically serve biobank data.

This deliverable reports primarily on aim #1 (sections 5 and 6), while aim #2 is mainly covered by the acquisition of biobank specific datasets and data characteristics as described in section 4. The modeling specifications (e.g. interaction diagrams, services, mockups, ...) produced by the deliverable will be re-used by future tasks.

3.3 User requirements

The services developed for T5.1 explore: 1. the search of EGA datasets, including user query expansion; 2. the selection of specific studies within the returned datasets, likely to contain pre-analytical data; 3. the querying of the data available within these studies; 4. the visualization of the data according to different criteria (e.g. count of samples with some particular characteristics). Figure 1 shows how services developed in T5.1 are also being re-used to support subsequent tasks.

Figure 1: Dataset search, expansion and exploration layers developed for D5.1 will be re-used by subsequent WP5 tasks and deliverables. In contrast, layers #4 and #5 are use-case specific. On the left side of the figure, #1 #2 and #3 refers respectively to WP1, 2 and 3, which corresponds to the following three layers: Query expansion services, Data search/Normalization, Data exploration with ontologies.

During the 1st year of CINECA, various types of queries were shared with the WP1 in order to 1) guide the development of query expansion services, and 2) discuss typical Beacon queries that might be interesting to formulate. For example, a user might want to ask “Search for data on BRCA gene mutations and the estrogen signaling pathway in women with stage I breast cancer” or “Find data about melanoma and BRAF V600E or V600K mutations”. Similarly, it was necessary to discuss with WP3 the content of the synthetic cohorts and to address the standardization of fields of interest. It was also necessary to prioritize and simulate some tasks to accommodate the parallel progress of different tasks.

4. Data management

4.1 Data acquisition

In a standard data lifecycle, the datasets stored in repositories are generally available under specific conditions, these conditions being even stricter when dealing with sensitive data such as human genomic data. In addition to the datasets, related metadata are registered in a searchable catalogue to make it discoverable by researchers. Once the datasets of interest are selected, users can request full access by contacting the DAC (Data Access Committee) and must then wait for the DAC to validate their demand. If approved, the final Data Acquisition (DAQ) phase can then follow. However, all these steps are usually asynchronous, and finding relevant data can be quite time and effort-consuming (due to incomplete or inconsistent metadata, difficulty to assess the validity/usability of the dataset for secondary use, etc.). Thus, T5.1 aims at facilitating this process through a centralized workflow, from search up to a visualization to help the researcher to get an overview of the data. Indeed several access modalities are possible, ranging from full access with local downloading rights or controlled access via aggregated contents as stored in a Beacon¹. *Beacon* is an open standard for genomics data discovery, developed by members of the Global Alliance for Genomics & Health. Originally developed to expose variant-related contents, it expanded to expose other biological entities.

Data acquisition (DAQ) is the process of retrieving information either in real time via APIs or through massive data collection and regular updates. In T5.1, the DAQ is considered as a full-fledged module. It gathers all the independent dedicated services associated with either the search index - ElasticSearch - or the internal and external APIs, and every query goes through the custom-built proxy.

¹ <https://beacon-project.io/>

4.2 Search services

The search capabilities of the system is key to make the datasets findable: the users should be able to find the relevant datasets easily for their research through a user-friendly interface.

T5.1 is designed to integrate the query expansion services developed by the WP1 in its search module, with the aim of supporting the user querying process [2,3]. For a comprehensive overview of the CINECA query expansion services, we refer to D1.2. Depending on the type of expansion, the user may retrieve much more pertinent documents by adding new words (synonyms, hypernyms, hyponyms, etc.) into the query field, or he can enlarge the scope of its research. Moreover, the EGA studies and datasets may be filtered using multiple facets that do not require a deep knowledge of the API parameters to obtain some relevant results. And finally, the visualization step uses the cohort normalized fields to make aggregate queries without needing to know the structure of the datasets nor the data endpoint algebra.

E.g. simple query: “Show me all the documents about pancreatic cancer”. We use the concept of simple query to refer to the search for a dataset that might be of interest to the researcher.

E.g. aggregated query: “How many individuals do we have with Biermer’s anemia and hypertension ?”. We use the concept of aggregated query to talk about a more advanced search on the specific content of a dataset.

4.3 Biobank data schema

For the sake of T5.1 use cases, we leveraged UK BioBank dataset [4] added a set of pre-analytical fields to it, including whole blood volume, processing temperature, storage temperature, and centrifuge pRBCs volume, following the methodology already explored by WP3 for several cohort contents.

5. Service specification

5.1 UML diagrams

The user/system interaction has been specified using UML specific diagrams that we created based on the preliminary specifications of WP5 use-cases [5,6,7]. The sequence diagram is an interaction diagram that shows how the operations are carried out. It is very valuable in the context of a collaboration between the different parts of a system that realizes a use case (or multiple systems). This type of diagram is time focused and it shows the order of the interaction visually by using the vertical axis to represent the time: which actor sends a message and when. The horizontal axis shows the elements (actors) that are involved in the processes. In Figure 2, the diagram represents the interaction between a user (researcher), the exploration tool (T5.1), the repository (EGA), and also the DAC. In Figure 3, the diagram

shows how the user can interrogate the same exploration tool, but overcoming the authorization waiting phase to get the data available in Beacon immediately.

Figure 2 : Sequence diagram of the prototype D5.1: Classical workflow. Up to step 10, the workflow supports the integration of WP1-3 CINECA services to advance biobank search.

Figure 3 : Sequence diagram of the prototype D5.1: Beacon workflow

The activity diagram is a behavioral diagram that represents how activities are coordinated to provide a service which can be at different levels of abstraction. Typically, an event needs to be achieved by some operations that can be sequential or concurrent. The activity diagrams have a beginning (an initial state) and an end (a final state), and in between we can describe activities, flows, decisions, guards, merge, time events, and more. Here, we have chosen to present two activity diagrams in complement to the previous sequence diagrams, however the actions represented are a bit redundant. In Figure 4, we visualize the behavior of the user, the exploration system, and the repository from the beginning of a search, until the user is asked for a DAC form, fills it out and waits. In Figure 5, we draw the shortened path between the start of a search and the statistical display of any information found in Beacon.

Figure 4 : Activity diagram of the classic search using the prototype D5.1.

Figure 5 : Activity diagram of the Beacon search using the prototype D5.1.

5.2 Service architecture

On the front-end, the T5.1 demonstrator is provided with a graphical user interface developed using the JavaScript/REACT technologies (cf. screenshots in paragraph 6.2). The visualization charts are created using the frameworks vue.js and chart.js. To have a more user-responsive tool, the call to the query expansion APIs are made asynchronously. On the back-end, the demonstrator implements a search engine connected to an Elasticsearch (ES) index, and a proxy that handles all the data sources' APIs.

ES allows us to index all the metadata and make them searchable for keyword-oriented queries. ES was also used as a substitution way to access the cohorts' data at the time the CINECA WPs were developing and normalizing them (CoLaus cohort, etc.). Indeed, the system has been developed to be modular and also connected to the Beacon network. To experiment with this, WP5 has deployed a local Beacon endpoint (<https://beacon.text-analytics.ch/>). The local instance is used as a gateway to access the cohort data, which have been provisionally loaded. Future updates will include conformance with the recently published GA4GH Beacon V2² standard. The demonstrator is currently able to model the search process and offers either a generic form to simulate a request for access to the DAC or a specific module capable of aggregating user queries and formulating complex questions such as “How many individuals do we have with Biermer’s anemia and hypertension?”

The source code of this demonstrator is available at GitHub: <https://github.com/bitem-heg-geneve/cineca-c51>

² <https://beacon-project.io/categories/beaconv2.html>

the number of concurrent users increases up to 10 users, while the response time remains flat (1.2 seconds on average, total of 720 requests), which is an indirect evaluation of the scalability of the services. The bandwidth metric shows the amount of data transferred, which can be interpreted as the network load on the server during times of high query traffic (sent: 655 KiB, received: 576 MiB). However, regarding the CPU and the memory usage, it does not indicate a high usage of the resources at any time during the evaluation (respectively 18% and 35% on average); thus confirming that memory/CPU bottlenecks remain unlikely to occur while scaling up within reasonable limits. Last but not least, the error rate of 0% shows that no problem occurs during the test.

Figure 7: Result of the load test on T5.1 simulation of a Beacon search.

Figure 7 displays the results of the load test on the second critical step of T5.1 workflow. Using the same parameters as for the previous test, the response time has slightly increased, with an average of about 1.6 second (713 requests). We estimate that this difference is due to the display of graphics (cohort statistics). Regarding the bandwidth, the traffic is slightly higher and characterized by small peaks depending on the kind of request (sent: 681 KiB, received: 569 MiB), but the CPU and memory usage remain stable (18% and 34% on average). The error rate is still at 0%.

An endurance test would allow us to verify the continuity of these measures over a longer period of time, while a stress test would allow us to estimate the limits of the system. However, as it stands, we can affirm that our system is very robust under conditions of use that we already consider reasonable in comparison with the use that could be made of such a tool.

6.2 Benchmark-based evaluation

We evaluated the accuracy search functionalities by evaluating both recall and precision of the demonstrator w/o using the query expansion services as well as the variant expansion services on two independent - yet complementary - search tasks. First, we search the literature w/o the expansion services. Second, we compare the search of the literature vs. the search of supplementary data, in a way which models a search for tabular data contents, which account for a large fraction of cohort related contents into repositories such as EGA. We design the search into a dataset repository with relatively heterogeneous files such as XLS, CSV, as well as images (e.g. GIF, JPEG), etc.

6.2.1 Data description

The evaluation of query expansion was done on three literature datasets: MEDLINE abstracts, the PMC full-text articles and the supplementary materials, attached to the publications. All MEDLINE abstracts (~33 millions) and PMC full-texts (~4.4 millions) were used for comparing documents retrieval w/o query expansion. For the evaluation of supplementary data, a subset of the literature was searched corresponding to 650,000 PMC IDs containing specific terms (gene, variant, polymorphism or mutation). In the absence of information retrieval benchmark to assess user information search in cohort/biobank data, this last dataset, which contains mostly tabular data (e.g. XLS, CSV) must be regarded as relatively similar to typical cohort data, while the MEDLINE and PMC datasets are only used as baseline for sake of comparison. An example of Tabular data is shown in Figure 8 below.

The queries consisted of a random set of BRCA1 and BRCA2 variants from the LOVD⁴ (*Leiden Open Variation Database v.2.0*) dataset, (e.g. *BRCA1(I1275V)*). All BRCA1 and BRCA2 missense SNPs (n=766) were used for query expansion evaluation and all nonsynonymous SNPs (n=803) were used for supplementary data evaluation.

⁴ <https://www.lovd.nl/>

Annotation	Allele Frequency	Name	GeneSymbol	ClinicalSignificance	PhenotypeList	OriginSimple
missense	0.41	NM_007294.3(BRCA1):c.2612C>T (p.Pro871Leu)	BRCA1	Benign	Breast-ovarian cancer, familial 1	germline/somatic
missense	0.3496	NM_007294.3(BRCA1):c.4837A>G (p.Ser1613Gly)	BRCA1	Benign	Breast-ovarian cancer, familial 1	germline/somatic
synonymous	0.3483	NM_007294.3(BRCA1):c.2082C>T (p.Ser694=)	BRCA1	Benign	Breast-ovarian cancer, familial 1	germline/somatic
missense	0.349	NM_007294.3(BRCA1):c.3548A>G (p.Lys1183Arg)	BRCA1	Benign	Breast-ovarian cancer, familial 1	germline

Supplementary table 4. BRCA1 variants identified in Chinese population

Variant ID	Exon*	HGVS		Genome (hg19)
		cDNA (NM_007294.3)	Protein (NP_009225.1)	
1	2	c.-7G>A	-	g.41276120C>T
2	2	c.-2A>T	-	g.41276115T>A
3	2	c.2T>G	p.Met1Arg	g.41276112A>C
4	2	c.3G>C	p.Met1Ile	g.41276111C>G
5	2	c.3G>T	p.Met1Ile	g.41276111C>A
6	2	c.17_18del	p.Leu6fs	g.41276096_41276097del
7	2	c.34C>T	p.Gln12Ter	g.41276080G>A
8	2	c.43A>G	p.Ile15Val	g.41276071T>C
9	2	c.57G>C	p.Gln19His	g.41276057C>G
10	2	c.62dupT	p.Glu23Argfs	g.41276052dupA
11	2	c.66dupA	p.Leu22fs	g.41276048dupT
12	2	c.66insA	p.Glu23ArgfsTer18	g.41276048dupT
13	2	c.68_69delAG	p.Glu23Valfs	g.41276045_41276046delC
14	2	c.70T>G	p.Cys24Gly	g.41276044A>C
15	2	c.80+1G>A	-	g.41276033C>T
16	2	c.80+1G>T	-	g.41276033C>A
17	2	c.81_134del54	p.Cys27Ter	g.41267743_41267796delC

Supplementary table 2. Clinical information for the patients reported by the studies*

Characteristics	Number	Percentage
Age at diagnosis		
≤50	4'242	62.3
>50	2'567	37.7
BMI		
< 18.5	177	10.5
18.5 - 22.9	1'417	83.7
> 22.9	99	5.8
Family history		
Yes	6'242	27.7
No	16'294	72.3
Tumor type		
Breast cancer	25'856	91
Ovarian cancer	2'469	8.7
Both	80	0.3
Histological type		
Ductal	16'306	89.9
Lobular	563	3.1
Other	1'162	6.4
Unknown	107	0.6
Grade at diagnosis /TNM Stage		
I	143	6.3
II	1'508	66.2
III	560	24.6
IV	12	0.5
Unknown	56	2.5
Metastases		
Lung	49	43.8
Bone	34	30.4
Liver	18	16.1
Brain	11	9.8
Tumor size		
T1	7'527	42.3
T2	9'616	54.1
T3	637	3.6

Figure 8: Examples of tabular supplementary data with variants and other clinical features (from PMC6327376 and PMC6617753).

6.2.2 Measures

The most frequent expansion patterns encountered in the literature corresponded to protein and transcript levels of variant description, followed by dbSNP IDs (Table 1).

Pattern	Example	Proportion
[A-Z]\d+[A-Z]	I1275V	37%
\d+\s*[ACGT]\s*>\s*[ACGT]	3823 A > G	28%
[A-Z][a-z]{2}\d+[A-Z][a-z]{2}	Ile1275Val	27%
rs\d+	rs80357280	11%
Others	3823A/G	1%

Table 1: Most frequent variant patterns encountered in the biomedical literature.

As shown in Table 2, using query expansion more than doubled the number of retrieved documents and nearly halved the number of queries without results. Symmetrically, the impact of query expansion on precision remains modest (93% compared to the baseline performed without query expansion), while the impact of searching in supplementary data was slightly more detrimental to precision but still moderate on the precision, i.e. 75%.

	Without query expansion (Medline, PMC)	With query expansion (Medline, PMC)	With query expansion + Suppl. Data (Medline, PMC+Suppl. data)
Average number of documents retrieved per query	3	7	18
Number of queries with no results	33%	18%	1%
Estimated precision	100% (5 variants, 27 documents)	93% (5 variants, 27 documents)	75% (*) (2 variants, 20 documents)

**only suppl. data*

Table 2: Evaluation of the query expansion on literature retrieval.

6.2.3 Error analysis

All the detected errors came from variants matched with the wrong gene. Supplementary data files, like tabular cohorts, often contain hundreds of variants from many different genes

or gene products, thus significantly increasing the likelihood of errors. This explains why searching in supplementary data slightly decreases the precision, however the gain wrt to recall remains in favor of using supplementary materials, in particular for rare variants, which are also more difficult to curate. The expansion service is beneficiary for all indexes but is it especially effective to gain recall when applied to supplementary data, while the drop of precision remains relatively modest.

6.3 Demonstration

Demonstrator URL: <http://denver.hesge.ch/cineca/demo/>

Scenario:

When landing on the homepage of the demonstrator, the user can perform a basic search by typing the keywords of his choice (e.g. “pancreatic neoplasms”) in the search field in the middle of the screen (Figure 9). Optionally, if he is not sure of his search, he can ask the query expansion service to propose other/additional keywords to expand his search. For example, “gastrinoma” and “insulinoma” (Figure 10) are concepts descending from “pancreatic neoplasms” in the MeSH ontology and thus they are suggested by the Vertical Expansion (see D1.2 Query Expansion Services for the definition) for a more specific research. Yet, query expansion is highly dependent on the type of query performed. For optimal performances, the user may a priori select one of the expansion options proposed in the dedicated section with the radio buttons.

Figure 9: Homepage of the demonstrator and search interface for biobank studies/datasets.

pancreatic neoplasms

Query example: BRCA1

Query expansion

Select the query expansion model

Vertical expansion Data-driven expansion Variant expansion

Show expansion

gastrinoma × insulinoma ×

Figure 10: Use of the advanced QE options on the search interface.

With regards to variants, there are so many different ways to describe the same variation, so it is sometimes difficult to find all the desired information with a simple query. The ability to manually refine the results of the expansion is therefore important. While the recommended way to describe variants is at the DNA level on a recent genomic build (e.g. NC_000011.10:g.31801697C>T), it is much more frequently described at the transcript or protein levels (e.g. 221G>A) as exemplified above in the QE evaluation of section 6.2. For example, PAX6 mutation causing ophthalmic disease is described in EGA studies at the transcript level (Figure 11) but it is not findable in the standard genomic description or protein level description. It therefore makes sense to use the QE service to select multiple variant formats and prioritize them in the results.

Studies related to query "Ser74Asn PAX6 OR c.221G>A"

100 studies with your filters (Total: 100 studies)

Study ID	Title	Study type	Year	Description	Study abstract
EGAS00001005873	Whole exome sequencing of Congenital Cataract	Other	2021	Whole exome sequencing to identify potentially relevant mutations of congenital cataract in a Chinese girl. The novel PAX6 mutation c.221G>A is associated with congenital cataract, and the WFS1 mutation (c.2070_2076del) interactively aggravates this process.	Whole exome sequencing to identify potentially relevant mutations of congenital cataract in a Chinese girl. The novel PAX6 mutation c.221G>A is associated with congenital cataract, and the WFS1 mutation (c.2070_2076del) interactively aggravates this process.
phs001276	Single-cell Profiling of an In Vitro Model of Human Interneuron Development Reveals Temporal Dynamics of Cell Type Production and Maturation	Single Cell Analysis	2017	GABAergic interneurons are essential for neural circuit function and their loss or dysfunction is implicated in human neuropsychiatric disease. In vitro methods for interneuron generation hold promis...	Single-cell Profiling of an In Vitro Model of Human Interneuron Development Reveals Temporal Dynamics of Cell Type Production and Maturation
phs000430	Hepatitis C Antiviral Long-term Treatment Against Cirrhosis (HALT-C)	Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial	2012	Reprinted from http://www.haltctrial.org/ Purpose The Hepatitis C Antiviral Long-term Treatment against Cirrhosis (HALT-C) Trial is a randomized controlled trial designed to evaluate the safety and e...	Hepatitis C Antiviral Long-term Treatment Against Cirrhosis (HALT-C)
EGAS00001005014	Primary prostate Hi-C	Cancer-Genomics			Prostate cancer is a heterogeneous disease whose progression is linked to genome instability. Despite large-scale tumour sequencing efforts, the impact of mutations on the genetic architecture in canc...
EGAS00001002517	Distinct genomic profile and specific targeted drug responses in adult cerebellar glioblastoma	Other	2018	Only a few studies have reported the molecular characteristics of adult cerebellar glioblastoma (C-GBM), a subtype comprising 1% of glioblastoma cases located within the infratentorial brain region du...	Only a few studies have reported the molecular characteristics of adult cerebellar glioblastoma (C-GBM), a subtype comprising 1% of glioblastoma cases located within the infratentorial brain region du...

Figure 11: Top results in EGA studies for the query "Ser74Asn PAX6 OR c.221G>A".

After a search, the user is redirected to a results page displaying the studies from the EGA database related to the original query. Out of the metadata made available through the EGA API, we decided to present the studies with the following fields: identifiers, titles, categories, years of publication, abstracts and descriptions (Figure 12) but all EGA meta-data could potentially be displayed. On the left of the page, filters help the user to navigate through the results (date ranges, study types, released status). And finally, on this page, the user can select one or more studies and request access to the related datasets. As presented on Figure 13, a dedicated panel then displays the EGA metadata about the selected datasets

(identifiers, titles, dataset types, description, acecs type, etc.). From this point, the user can request the right of access to the full data from the respective DAC (Figure 14), or navigate to the “Beacon panel” seeking information necessary for his research while waiting for an answer from the DAC. The DAC form here plays the role of the AAI/REMS component of WP2.

Studies related to query "pancreatic neoplasms"

100 studies with your filters (Total: 100 studies)

Beacon explorer

Go to Beacon explorer

Sort

By rank

By study ID

By data

By selection

Filters

Data

0 2021

Study type

Other (41)

Cancer Genomics (23)

Case Set (5)

Whole Genome Sequencing (7)

Cohort (5)

Released

RELEASED (76)

NOT_RELEASED (24)

Selected	Study ID	Title	Study type	Year	Description	Study abstract
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EGAS00001004473	Evolutionary analysis of pancreatic neoplasia cysts through whole-exome and targeted sequencing	Other	2020	Intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasms (IPMNs) and mucinous cystic neoplasms (MCNs) are non-invasive neoplasms that are often observed in association with invasive pancreatic cancers, but their orig...	Intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasms (IPMNs) and mucinous cystic neoplasms (MCNs) are non-invasive neoplasms that are often observed in association with invasive pancreatic cancers, but their orig...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EGAS00001005024	Proteogenomic classification and characterization of pancreatic neuroendocrine neoplasms	Other	2021	Pancreatic neuroendocrine neoplasms (PNETs) are biologically and clinically heterogeneous neoplasms. We used a multi-omics approach to uncover the molecular factors underlying the heterogeneity and d...	Pancreatic neuroendocrine neoplasms (PNETs) are biologically and clinically heterogeneous neoplasms. We used a multi-omics approach to uncover the molecular factors underlying the heterogeneity and d...
<input type="checkbox"/>	EGAS00001004801	Bulk-RNA Sequencing of high-grade pancreatic and non-pancreatic Neuroendocrine Neoplasms	Other	2020	Therapeutic decisions in oncology depend on a precise pathological classification of individual neoplasms. Recent years have seen an intensification of research activities aimed at the extraction of...	Therapeutic decisions in oncology depend on a precise pathological classification of individual neoplasms. Recent years have seen an intensification of research activities aimed at the extraction of...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EGAS00001005731	DNA methylation and Panel sequencing for pancreatic neuroendocrine carcinomas (PanNECs) and pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors (PanNETs)	Cancer Genomics	2021		Pancreatic Neuroendocrine Neoplasms (PanNETs) are two subclasses of the well-differentiated, low to high-grade Pancreatic Neuroendocrine Tumors (PanNETs) and the poorly-differentiated, high-grade Pancre...
<input type="checkbox"/>	phs000871	Whole Exome Sequencing of Pancreatic Neuroendocrine Tumors at The Human Genome Sequencing Center, Baylor College of Medicine (HGSC-BCM)	Cohort	2015	Pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors (PNETs), often referred to as "islet cell tumors", are neuroendocrine neoplasms that arise from cells of the endocrine and nervous system within the pancreas. These r...	Whole Exome Sequencing of Pancreatic Neuroendocrine Tumors at The Human Genome Sequencing Center, Baylor College of Medicine (HGSC-BCM)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EGAS00001001573	The genetic evolution of precursor lesions in pancreatic cancer	Cancer Genomics	2016	Mapping genetic evolution of pancreatic cancer precursor lesions such as IPMNs and PanINs.	This study aims to map the genetic evolution of precursor lesions such as IPMNs (intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasms) and PanINs (pancreatic intraepithelial neoplasias) into invasive pancreatic c...
<input type="checkbox"/>	phs002045	Intraductal transplantation models of human pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma reveal progressive transition of molecular subtypes	Case Set	2020	Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) is the most lethal common malignancy, with little improvement in patient outcomes over the past few decades. Recently, subtypes of pancreatic cancer with diffe...	Intraductal transplantation models of human pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma reveal progressive transition of molecular subtypes
<input type="checkbox"/>	EGAS00001001041	Evolution of the cancer epigenome in myeloproliferative neoplasms	Cancer Genomics	2019	Evolution of the cancer epigenome in myeloproliferative neoplasms.	Cancer clones emerge and evolve through somatic mutation acquisition and Darwinian selection, but the dynamics of clonal evolution remain poorly understood and predicting disease progression remains a...
<input type="checkbox"/>	EGAS00001000303	MPN bisulphite	Cancer Genomics		Evolution of the cancer epigenome in myeloproliferative neoplasms.	Cancer clones emerge and evolve through somatic mutation acquisition and Darwinian selection, but the dynamics of clonal evolution remain poorly understood and predicting disease progression remains a...
<input type="checkbox"/>	EGAS00001005208	WIGMS MPN PDS183	Whole Genome Sequencing		Whole genome methylation sequencing of colonies of patients with myeloproliferative neoplasms.	Whole genome methylation sequencing of colonies of patients with myeloproliferative neoplasms.

[<<](#)
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[3](#)
[...](#)
[10](#)
[>](#)
[>>](#)

[Show all studies](#)

[Expand/Details](#)

Figure 12: Study interface, with EGA documents resulting from the query “pancreatic neoplasms”.

Datasets of selected studies: EGAS00001000395,phs000206

Study EGAS00001000395 - Pancreatic Cancer Sequencing Initiative OICR

Selected Dataset id Title Dataset types Description Beacon Access type Center name Technologies

EGAS00001001595 ICGC PACA-CA Release 18 Whole genome sequencing,Exome sequencing,Transcriptome profiling by high-throughput sequencing,Transcriptome profiling by array,Amplikon sequencing Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC Illumina HiSeq 2000,Illumina HiSeq 2500

EGAS00001001596 ICGC PACA-CA Release 20 sample ICGC PACA-CA Release 20 Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC Illumina HiSeq 2000,Illumina HiSeq 2500

EGAS00001001598 ICGC PACA-CA Release21 Whole genome sequencing,Exome sequencing ICGC Release 21 for PACA-CA from OICR Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC Illumina HiSeq 2000,Illumina HiSeq 2500

EGAS00001003263 PACA-CA WGS_deep_sequencing alignments in support of PACA-CA ICGC Release 24 Amplikon sequencing ICGC DCC Release 24, PACA-CA Deep KRAS sequencing Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC

EGAS00001003384 Pancreatic Cancer OICR Exome sequencing ICGC DCC Release 24, PACA-CA Exome sequence Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC

EGAS00001003270 Pancreatic Cancer OICR Whole genome sequencing ICGC DCC Release 24, PACA-CA Whole Genome sequence merged alignments Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC

EGAS00001003591 PACA-CA Whole Genome Sequence bam files Merged bam files for PACA-CA Whole Genome Sequencing, for DCC release 25 Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC

EGAS00001003592 PACA-CA Whole Exome Sequence bam files Exome sequencing Merged bam files for PACA-CA Whole Exome Sequencing, for DCC release 25 Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC

EGAS00001003597 PACA-CA Whole Genome Sequence bam files Whole genome sequencing Merged bam files for PACA-CA Whole Genome Sequencing, for DCC release 27 Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC

EGAS00001003546 PACA-CA RNASeq bam files Transcriptome profiling by high-throughput sequencing Bam files for PACA-CA RNA Seq analysis, for DCC release 27 Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC

EGAS00001003548 PACA-CA Whole Genome Sequence bam files Whole genome sequencing Merged bam files for PACA-CA Whole Genome Sequencing, for DCC release 27 Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC

EGAS00001003972 PACA-CA RNASeq test files Transcriptome profiling by high-throughput sequencing Fastq files for PACA-CA RNA Seq analysis, for DCC release 27 Yes CONTROLLED OICR_ICGC ILLUMINA,Illumina HiSeq 2500

EGAS00010001513 CIV_ARRAY sample Copy Number Variation as determined on Illumina Omni Arrays Yes CONTROLLED Illumina Beadchip

Study phs000206 - Whole Genome Scan for Pancreatic Cancer Risk in the Pancreatic Cancer Cohort Consortium and Pancreatic Cancer Case-Control Consortium (PanScan)

Selected Dataset id Title Dataset types Description Beacon Access type Center name Technologies

datasets not found

[Request/Get access](#)

Figure 13: Dataset interface, with EGA documents related to the studies selected in the previous panel.

Data Access Committees request (DACs)

Selected dataset: EGAD00001006229

First name:

Surname:

Organization:

Position/role:

Address:

Telephone:

Email:

Check here if you are requesting access only for yourself (no additional collaborators)

Please provide a description of your research plan and the intended use of the data

[Request access](#)

Figure 14: DAC request interface.

The “Beacon panel” is the last interface accessible from the user, which aims to streamline access and clinical analysis to some discovered datasets using CINECA cohort endpoints. Here, the user reformulates his request and the interface displays the information retrieved on the network.

Concretely, there are 3 search fields named “Disease”, “Variant”, and “Other” to orient the search respectively on a disease name, a mutation, or specific normalized fields (Figure 15). To simplify the demonstration, we focussed the information retrieval to the 4 synthetic datasets available for CINECA (namely CoLaus, CHILD, H3A and UKB). All together, these 4 datasets represent 340 data fields out of which seven fields were normalized using WP3 services (i.e. age, gender, height, weight, cancer, hypertension, diabetes). Moreover, we added 2 + 6 custom data fields respectively for variants and pre-analytical data (see paragraph 4.3). The statistics are displayed with bar charts, and the “unknown” bar represents the absence of one type of data in the selected cohorts.

Figure 15: Visualization charts available for cohorts' sample data.

7. Conclusion and next steps

In this deliverable, we developed a data exploration service and a demonstrator to explore BioBanks data. The system customizes the full stack of CINECA services from datasets search to access and visualization. Normalization of contents is based on W3 services. The evaluation of both efficiency and effectiveness of the search platform suggests that the services are robust and likely to significantly enhance the ability of end-users to discover datasets.

8. References

- [1] Public Copy of Initial Use Case Metadata Requirements
- [2] D1.2 Query expansion service
- [3] Query Expansion - Introduction, [Query Expansion - Introduction — CINECA - Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa](#)
- [4] CINECA synthetic cohort EUROPE UK1 referencing fake samples, <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001006673>
- [5] CINECA Use Cases v1.0
- [6] WP2 Lead_Roadmap Agenda_2020 February, [WP2 Lead_Roadmap Agenda_2020 February](#)
- [7] WP5.1 use cases

9. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
BB	BioBank
DAC	Data Access Committee
DAQ	Data acquisition
ES	ElasticSearch
GA4GH	The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (https://www.ga4gh.org), a standards body for health genomics APIs and data models.

GECKO	Genomics Cohorts Knowledge Ontology, an ontology to represent genomics cohort attributes. Browse: https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/gecko Description of GECKO's development: https://github.com/IHCC-cohorts/GECKO
GUI	Graphical User Interface
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LOVD	Leiden Open Variation Database
MeSH	Medical Subject Headings (https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html) thesaurus is a controlled and hierarchically-organized vocabulary produced by the National Library of Medicine used for indexing, cataloging, and searching of biomedical and health-related information.
NCIt	National Cancer Institute Thesaurus
QE	Query Expansion
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modeling Language
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System (https://www.nlm.nih.gov/research/umls/index.html), is a set of files and software that brings together many health and biomedical vocabularies and standards to enable interoperability between computer systems.
WP	Work package

10. Work Packages in CINECA

WP1 - Federated Data Discovery and Querying

WP2 - Interoperable Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

WP3 - Cohort Level Meta Data Representation

WP4 - Federated Joint Cohort Analysis

WP5 - Healthcare Interoperability and Clinical Applications

WP6 - Outreach, training and dissemination

WP7 - Ethical and legal governance framework for transnational data-sharing

WP8 - Project Management and coordination

WP9 - Ethics requirements

11. Delivery and schedule

The delivery has been delayed by 6 months.

12. Appendices

None.

